

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF SELF-CONFIDENCE AND SELF- RELATIONSHIP IN ADOLESCENT PERSONALITY

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Abstract. The article puts forward theoretical views on the manifestation of self-attitude in adolescence. Especially in adolescence, the influence of self-confidence on the formation of self-esteem was studied on the basis of empirical data.

Key words: adolescent, personality, self-esteem, self-confidence, self-esteem, self-esteem, self-respect, autosympathy.

Introduction. One of the most important features of adolescence is self-awareness and understanding oneself as a person. Adolescents develop an interest in themselves, their inner life, and personal qualities, as well as a need for self-evaluation and comparing themselves with others. The need for self-awareness arises from life and practical activities and is determined by the increasing demands of older members of the group. In order to find their place in the community, adolescents need to assess their own abilities.

Literature review. In Russian psychology, personality is manifested as a system of an individual's attitudes toward the surrounding reality, within which three components stand out: attitude toward oneself, toward others, and toward the world in general [1]. The first component is the most important because it participates in every process of an individual's manifestation as a social subject.

N.F. Kravsova considers self-attitude as a multidimensional, structurally layered component of self-awareness—a relatively stable personal characteristic actively maintained by the individual [5].

A.D. Astresov understands it as the expression of the meaning of "I" for a person—a stable positive or negative feeling toward oneself, consisting of two subsystems: the self-esteem system and the system of emotional-value relations [2]. It gradually develops as the individual becomes included in a system of relationships with others and through the results of personal activity [6]. A child's self-attitude directly depends on the nature of the attitude toward them in their immediate environment. As the social circle matures and expands, the content of self-attitude is supplemented by influences beyond family relations. Gradually, the role of social interactions in shaping self-attitude shifts to a decisive role in forming a person's leading life position and behavioral patterns. It is also widely recognized that self-attitude has a complex structure.

Emotional and evaluative attitudes toward oneself result from processes of social comparison or comparison with socially accepted norms and ideals. A person can observe this unique internal attitude independently. It depends on current life experience and can change. As we grow older, two subsystems become balanced [7].

Depending on whether positive, negative, or ambivalent (conflicting) manifestations toward oneself dominate, three corresponding modalities can be distinguished—positive, negative, and ambivalent [8].

As the affective component of self-awareness, self-attitude cannot be considered neutral by the cognitive component (self-knowledge); instead, it evokes appropriate evaluations and emotions. To describe the emotional component of self-awareness, the term “emotional-value-based self-attitude” is often used. This construct reflects a person’s attitude toward what they have learned and discovered about themselves.

L.V. Borozdina believes that three elements of self-awareness should not be confused: self-image, self-esteem, and self-attitude—even though they merge as the individual develops [4]. According to U. Molchanova, self-esteem is the foundation of the self-awareness process; it largely determines a person’s activity, governs behavior, and guides actions. It represents the individual’s awareness of the meaning of their self-knowledge for themselves and others. Its core embodies the values accepted by the person [2]. On the one hand, self-attitude reflects the individual’s position toward personal traits. On the other hand, it largely determines how the individual manifests themselves in relationships with the outside world. It enables a person to properly set priorities, correlate strengths and weaknesses, and determine future prospects (based on situations and personal capacities).

According to R.S. Nemov, the intensification of an adolescent’s need for individuation, combined with maximalism in others’ evaluations—who also strive to find and express their individuality—can complicate the development of self-attitude: “...individuation simultaneously evokes an acute need for self-expression and entering the inner world of another” [10].

Discussion. Using the model of favorable self-attitude presented in T.S. Levin’s work [9], we can identify the structure of optimal self-attitude or, as we may call it, favorable self-attitude for the adolescent’s personality. Considering that self-attitude itself has a complex structure, certain expressions and correlations of its components are considered favorable. Additionally, according to S. Pantelev [11], the structure of self-attitude includes the following components: closeness, self-confidence, self-management, reflected self-attitude, self-esteem, self-acceptance, self-attachment, internal conflict, and self-blame. If we describe the favorable expression of each scale more specifically, they can be characterized as follows:

1. Closeness (openness) — Low scores on this scale are considered favorable. This determines the level of sincerity toward oneself. In another sense, the adolescent may rely on a socially desirable image without allowing themselves to be genuine.

2. Self-esteem — High scores on the “self-respect” scale are positive.

3. Self-management — Favorably expressed at high functional levels. This indicates the person’s level of responsibility for choosing life positions. Conversely, lower levels lead the individual to feel that events depend mainly on those around them. However, very high scores also pose risk, as people who believe everything depends solely on themselves often struggle to accept what cannot be changed.

1. **Reflected self-attitude (“Reflective I”)** — This component measures the degree to which sympathy or antipathy toward oneself is perceived as reflecting others’ attitudes. Sympathetic attitudes from others are positive, but constant expectation of sympathy is unrealistic and increases vulnerability. When such a person encounters negative attitudes, they experience severe disappointment.

2. **Self-esteem (in the internal sense)** — High scores indicate that a person feels the value of their inner world and “Self.” This may serve as a driving force, as individuals who value

themselves but perform poorly in other areas may feel unrealized potential and be motivated to use their abilities.

3. **Self-acceptance** — High scores indicate emotional kindness toward oneself. This is fundamental for personal development. High self-acceptance does not mean lack of self-criticism; rather, it allows realistic self-perception, awareness of weaknesses and mistakes, and efforts to improve.

4. **Self-attachment** — Moderate scores are optimal; very high scores may indicate psychological rigidity and resistance to change, while very low scores may indicate dissatisfaction with oneself. Age and life circumstances should be considered when evaluating this scale.

5. **Internal conflict and self-blame** — Low scores are favorable. However, during “internal restructuring,” age-related or existential crises, temporary increases in these scores are natural.

Based on the above material, we can conclude that a favorable, optimal self-attitude in adolescents is characterized by high self-esteem, a sense of responsibility for life events, positive reflected self-attitude (without losing realism), high internal self-value, strong emotional self-acceptance, and low levels of internal conflict and self-blame.

A person with a positive attitude toward themselves allows openness toward oneself, meaning they do not hide their true self from themselves. If a person’s functioning falls within the average range, they may assume their self-attitude is similar to most people. However, for many, these values are far from optimal for psychological comfort.

Thus, forming self-attitude in adolescents primarily involves shaping personal identity, developing a reasonable attitude toward oneself as a subject of social activity, self-respect, and gaining the respect of peers. If an adolescent allows themselves to be authentic—accepting their strengths and weaknesses in their full diversity—this indicates the development, realism, and adaptive flexibility of their self-attitude.

Conclusion. Based on the theoretical analysis presented, we can draw the following conclusions:

Adolescence is considered an important stage in personality development.

The formation of self-confidence in adolescents occurs under the influence of reflective processes such as self-awareness, self-control, self-regulation, and self-education.

During adolescence, a strong positive correlation is observed between self-confidence and self-attitude, ensuring their mutually beneficial development.

The development of self-confidence in adolescence is influenced by the formation of views about life and the development of positive attitudes toward oneself.

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